

Mohacūrottara, caturthaḥ paṭalaḥ verses 1-42, edition

F f22r, line 3; G (the folios appear scrambled. I will refer to the digital image number) 008.tif, upper, line 4; H f11r, line 3.

4.1 ataḥ paraṃ pravakṣyāmi bhūmeś caiva parigrahaṃ
śalyoddhārādikaṃ sarvaṃ balikarma grhādikaṃ

4.2 saraḥsu nalinicchannanirastaraviraśmiṣu
haṃsakākṣiptakalhāravīthīvimalavīciṣu

4.3 haṃsakāraṇḍakākrauñcacakravākavirājiṣu
paryantapulinacchāyāvīśrāntajalavīciṣu

4.4 puṇyakṣetrādīśaileṣu nirjharopāntabhūmiṣu
nadītīre taḍāge vā vāpīpuṣkarīṇītate

F f22v

4.5 catvare dīrghikādyāsu śrīṅgāte ca catuṣpathe
ramante devatā nityaṃ vaneṣūpavaneṣu ca

4.6 grāmakheṭapurādaḥ tu svāmitvaṃ yatra vidyate
ādaḥ parīkṣya bhūbhāgaṃ varṇināṃ śubhaṃ icchatām

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4.7 sitā vipre nrpe raktā pītā vaiśye 'sitetare
dīpakhātajalenādaḥ varṇānāṃ lakṣayec chubhaṃ

Ω = F(→H)G

1b bhūmeś caiva] FH; bhūmivāstu G 2a cchanna] G; cchannaṃ FH

2c haṃsakākṣipta] F,G; haṃsakākṣika H 2d vīciṣu] FH; vāriṣu G

3a kāraṇḍakā] F; kāraṇḍavā GH 3c pulina] FG; pūrīta H

5b śrīṅgāte ca] H,F; śrīṅgāteṣu G 6a kheṭa] FH; kheṭa[[ka]] G

7b 'sitetare] conj.; sitetarā FGH

7d lakṣayec chubhaṃ] H,G; lakṣayetsubhaṃ F

4.8 pūrvaplavā nṛpasyoktā vaiśye syād dakṣiṇaplavā
udakplavā dvijātīnāṃ śūdrāṇāṃ paścimaplavā

4.9 pūrvottareśato nimnā sarvasādhāraṇā mahī F f23r
uptabījā tu saṃjātā tṛtīye hy uttamā mahī

4.10 pañcame madhyamā proktā saptame vādhamā smṛtā
yāmye nago vanam cāpye saumye sasyam harau jalam

4.11 nātimṛdvī na kaṭhinā sukhasparśā samā ghanā H f11v
snigdha gurvī dṛḍhā śuddhā sugandhā doṣavarjitā

4.12 svādūdakā na sphuṭitā surūpātīmanoharā
sagarbhā soṣarā cchidrā sasattvā ca saśoṇitā

4.13 pūtigandhādibhir duṣṭāṃ jñātvā samyak tyajen mahīm
evam parīkṣya bhūbhāgaṃ grāhyo doṣavivarjitaḥ

4.14 sadvāratithilagnenduyute 'hni jayamaṅgalaḥ
evam parigrahec chakra śivakumbhabhrameṇa tu

$\Omega = F(\rightarrow H)G$

9a pūrvottareśato] FH; pūrvottaregatau G 10c yāmye nago] FH; yāmyego G

10d sasyam] FH; śāsya G • harau] em. Sanderson; harer FGH

11a mṛdvī] FH; tṛdvī G 12c cchidrā FH; śuddhā G

13d doṣa] FH; dopa G 14a lagnendu] FH; lagneṣu G

14c parigrahec chakra] GH; parigrahetsakra F

4.15 sīmāṃ surakṣitāṃ kṛtvā sīmāśuddhipuraḥsaram
tataḥ prasārayet sūtram ācāryaḥ śilpibhir vṛtaḥ

F f23v

4.16 udīcīm dhruvavedhena prācīm vā dhruvatārayā
puṣyapauṣṇamaghāvedhād atha śaṅkvādisādhanaiḥ

4.17 evaṃ pūrvāparaṃ jñātvā madhye kaṃ pārśvayor nayet
matamānatulyasūtreṇa yathā syād dakṣiṇottaram

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4.18 tato 'py ardhaṃ samādāya vidikkṛṣṇeṣu lāñchayet
caturaśraṃ tataḥ kṛtvā navadhā vibhajet punaḥ

4.19 vāyavyānalarakṣeśagatau vaṃśau śacīpate
rajjvaṣṭakaṃ kartavyaṃ ṣaṭpadaṃ tripadaṃ hare

4.20 tataḥ sragbalidhūpādyaiḥ pūjayed vāstugān surān
tanmadhye pūjayet pṛthvīm dhārikām śaktirūpiṇīm

4.21 vāstuṃ saṃpūjayet paścād brahmāṇaṃ ca śacīpate
randhrādhipaṃ vijānīyān marīcyādyorasādhipān

Ω = F(→H)G

With 21c, compare BS 52.46: madhye brahmā navakoṣṭhakādhipaḥ

15a sīmāṃ] em. Sanderson; samāṃ FGH • rakṣitāṃ] em. Sanderson; takṣitāṃ FGH

15b śuddhipuraḥsaram] em. Sanderson; śuddhipuraḥsarām] FH; śuddhiḥpuraḥsarāḥ G

15d ācāryaḥ] FH; ācārya G

16a dhruva] FH; brahma G

17b madhye] G; madhyeṃ GH

• nayet] conj. Sanderson; viyat FGH 18a ardhaṃ] H; arddha FG

19b gatau] FG; gato H

19d tri] GH; tṛ F

20c tan] FH; tat G

21a vāstuṃ] H; vāstu FG

• paścād] H; paścāt FG

21b ca] FH; tu G

21d marīcyādyorasādhipān] conj.; marīcyādyorasādhipāḥ F;

marīcyādyārasādhipāḥ G; marīcyāṃghārasādhipāḥ H

- 4.22 dvipadā āpavatsādyā jñeyāś cāṣṭau surādhipa F f24r
 dvātriṃśad devatā bāhye harādyāḥ padikāsthitaḥ
- 4.23 brahmādiditiparyantāś catvāriṃśac ca pañca ca
 vāstvaṅge devatānām ca saṃkhyā hy eṣā puraṃdara
- 4.24 bahir īśac carakyādyāḥ skandādyāḥ pūrvataḥ sthitaḥ
 ity aṣṭau devatā bāhye evaṃ vāstunaraḥ sthitaḥ H f12r
- 4/25 indrādyā lokapāḥ pūjyā ye cānye tatsamāśritāḥ
 bhūtavargāś ca ye tatra sragdhūpabalibhir varaiḥ
- 4.26 sarvamarmamayo vāstus tasmāt pīḍāṃ na kārayet
 cālayitvā yavaṃ cārdhaṃ kiṃcit pūrvottaraṃ nayet
- 4.27 vāstau pracālite śakra marmaughaś calito bhavet
 evaṃ yat kriyate dhāma surāṇām vāstupūrvakam G 004.tif, lower
- 4.28 tad iṣṭasiddhaye jñeyam anyathā tu viparyayaḥ F f24v
 śākunoktyā janoktyā vā prāṇinām sūtralaṅghane
- 4.29 kaṇḍūyanādivijñānair jñātvā śalyaṃ samuddharet
 kaivalyajñānasampanno jyotiḥśāstravidhānavit

$\Omega = F(\rightarrow H)G$

with 28d, compare: BS 52.106cd: śvāśrgālalaṅghita vā sūtre śalyaṃ vinirdiśet

- 22b surādhipa] FH; surādhipaḥ G 22c triṃśad] GH; ṭṛṃsad F
 22d padikā] FH; padi G 23a brahmādiditi] FH; brahmāditi G
 24a īśac] em. Sanderson; īśādi FH; īśāt G
 • carakyādyāḥ] G; carakyādyā F; {ca}raky{ā}dyāḥ H
 24b skandādyāḥ] FH; skandādyā G
 25a lokapāḥ] FH; lokapālāśca G • pūjyā] GH; pūjyā{ḥ} F
 25b samāśritāḥ] H; samāśṛtāḥ FG 26b pīḍāṃ] FH; pīḍā G
 26c yavaṃ cārdhaṃ] em.; yavaṃvārdhāṃ FH; yavacārdhā G; F then repeats the half
 verse, using cārdhāṃ: [[cālayitvāyavaṃcārdhāṃkiṃcitpūrvottarannayet]

- 4.30 adhyātmajñānakuśalaḥ śalyoddhāre labhed yaśaḥ
jalāntaṃ karkarāntaṃ vā khaned vā ‡ roparodhataḥ ‡
- 4.31 karāpūrais tu pāṣāṇair mṛttikāṣṭāṅgulāntaraiḥ
tāvad āpūrayet khātaṃ yāvat pādonam āgatam
- 4.32 bhūtaṃ susamaṃ kṛtvā sūtrayitvā yathā purā
śilānyāsaṃ prakurvīta tāsāṃ saṃkṣepalakṣaṇam
- 4.33 turyāśrā hastamātrās tāḥ pañca vasvaṅgulocchritāḥ
pañcakajāṅkā ghaṭāḥ pañca ratnamadhvādīpūrītāḥ
- 4.34 pañcagavyakaṣāyādīdhautāḥ śuddhāḥ suveṣṭītāḥ
nandābhadraḥ jayāriktāpūrṇākhyābhiḥ supūjitāḥ
- 4.35 dharādītattvavinyastā budhyantapadagarbhitāḥ
tatrātmātattvaṃ mātrāntaṃ vidyātattvaṃ manontaram
- 4.36 garvabuddhī tṛtīye tu tatas tattvādhipān nyaset
salokape śive yaṣṭe hutāgnau saṃvibhājite
- 4/37 tarpiteṣu ca mantreṣu samastādhvani śodhite
nyaset tatra śilāvṛāte kumbhanyāsapuraḥsaram

F f25r

At F, 35ab is inserted from the bottom margin.

$\Omega = F(\rightarrow H)G$

With 30cd, compare: Somaśambhupaddhati 4.1.21: karkarāntaṃ jalāntaṃ vā
śalyadoṣajighāṃsayā | khānayed athavā jñātvā vidhinā śalyam uddharet ||.

- 30c vā] GH; [[ca]]vā F 30d khaned vāroparodhataḥ] FH; khanetbhāgeparodhataḥ G
31a pūrais] FH; pūras G • pāṣāṇair] FH; ayāśānair G
31b mṛttikāṣṭāṅgulāntaraiḥ] FH; mṛttikāṅgulāntaraiḥ G 32c nyāsaṃ] FH; samyat G
33a turyāśrā] G; caturasrā FH • mātrās tāḥ] FG; mātrāḥ H
34b dhautāḥ] em.; dhautā{ḥ} H; dhautā FG 35c mātrāntaṃ] FH; āyāntaṃ G
35d manontaram] FH; manontagaṃ G 36d tattvādhipān] FH; tatvādhipā G
37c nyaset] G; nyaste FH 37d kumbha] FH; kuṇḍa G
37d saram] em.; Sanderson; sare FGH

- 4.38 padmaṃ vātha mahāpadmaṃ śaṅkhaṃ marakataṃ tathā samudraṃ pañcamaṃ teṣu nāmamantrair viśodhanam G 004.tif upper
H f12v
- 4.39 pūjayitvā purā vāstuṃ madhye śaktiṃ niveśayet tasyopari samudrākhyam pūrṇam tasyordhvato nyaset F f25v
- 4.40 brahmādau vinyasec chaktiṃ padmādīnām niveśanam sthāpitavyāḥ sunandādyā bhittigarbhe suniścitaiḥ
- 4.41 ucchrayeṇottamaṃ pīṭhaṃ prāsādārdhena kīrtitam madhyamaṃ pādahīnaṃ tu uttamārdhena kanyasam
- 4.42 evam ācinuyāt pīṭhaṃ sulepaṃ sandhivarjitam garbhabhittyādivinyāsam tadūrdhvaṃ tu śacīpate

$\Omega = F(\rightarrow H)G$

- 38d mantrair] FH; mantri G • viśodhanam] FH; viśodhitam G
39c samudrākhyam] FH; mudrākhyam G 39d pūrṇam] FH; pūrṇākhyam G
40c sthāpitavyāḥ] FH; sthāpitasoḥ G 40d garbhe suniścitaiḥ] em. Sanderson;
garbhesuniścitāḥ H; garbhesuniscitāḥ F; garbheṣuniścitāḥ G
42b sulepaṃ] FH; sulep[[ā]]am G • sandhivarjitam] FH; sannivarjitaṃ G